

MIGRATION OF LAHAULI TRIBES OF HIMACHAL PRADESH: CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES

Purshottam

Guest Faculty, Department of Social Work, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana

Nidhi Saini

Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana

Vanita Dhingra

Professor & Chairperson, Department of Social Work, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana

Akshay Kumar

Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana

ABSTRACT

The present paper attempts to understand and explain the migration trends in Lahauli Tribes of Himachal Pradesh. The paper tries to find out the factors responsible for migration and to know the effects of migration on families left behind in the place of origin. For the purpose of this paper, a data of 200 samples were collected by using snow ball sampling from all the panchayats of Lahaul valley of Lahaul & Spiti district through the structured interview schedule.

The analysis shows that the poor health care facilities and less educational facilities along with harsh geographic conditions and lack of facilities in winters accounts for the out migration of Lahaulis. Not only the push factors, but the pull factors like boom in apple markets in Kullu, better income opportunities than Lahaul attracts Lahaulis towards Kullu. The paper also highlights the several concerns associated with Lahauli migration.

KEYWORDS: Tribal Migration, Lahaul & Spiti, Lahauli Tribes, Place of origin, Lahauli migrants

INTRODUCTION

Migration has been an integral part of human life since ancient times. The primitive man used to move from one place to another in search of food & livelihood. It has not been curbed even today, but the scope of nature and mobility has changed. The mobility of mankind increased with increasing population. Mostly people are migrating to lead better life, to get better jobs, good social security and higher education etc.

Migration is defined as a decision to change of residence from one civic location to another. The Universal declaration of Human Rights stated in article 13 that "everyone has right to freedom of movement and residence within the border of each state and everyone has right to leave any country, including his own and to return to his time".

Migration plays an important role in the life of human beings. No community is untouched by the impact of migration. Many research gives evidence that the tribes of India could not escape the effects of migration. Tribals are also facing many detriments in India due to migration. The population belonging to scheduled tribes (ST) is relatively socio-economically backward.

Circular and seasonal migration in India is high among scheduled castes (SCs) and scheduled tribes (STs). According to Dayal & Karan (2003), the migration among SCs & STs was nearly twice that of other upper castes. In the tribal dominated districts of southern Madhya Pradesh, approximately 65 per cent of households included migrants (Mosse et al., 1997). A study of twelve villages of tribal dominated state of Jharkhand revealed that one-third of the households had at least one member migrating out from the village in search of jobs. There is extremely high rate of migration among

tribals of Rajasthan too. They migrate to Gujarat to work in seed cotton farms and textile markets (Bird & Deshingkar, 2009).

The Lahauli tribes have their own history of migration. Migration has been the part and parcel of life of Lahaulis from the time immemorial. Lahaulis started migrating because they did not have decent income at the place of origin for livelihood. Harcourt (1871) writes that “the greater part of population of Lahaul used to migrate as the autumn sets in, and squat for work in various parts of Kullu valley, returning in the spring to their homes laden with supplies, either for sale in Ladakh or home consumption”. Agnew (1897), in the ‘Gazetteer of Kangra District’ also mentioned about the involvement of Lahaulis in trading with Ladakh and seasonal migration of poorer families to Shimla or Kullu for the winter to make money by working as coolies, or by keeping lugri¹ shops. Mamgain (1975) also wrote about Lahauli migration to Manali, Kullu & Shimla Hills with piles of wool and other articles of export during winters. Kumar (2004) says that “with the passes of time Lahaulis started migrating to other area of Himachal Pradesh in search of better living conditions. Lahaulis opted to migrate within the state boundaries to escape hardship of weather”. Initially the migration was temporary in nature in search of work thereafter the better living conditions and an economic opportunity motivated them for permanent settlement over the time.

But over the last few decades, the demography of Lahaul and Spiti District has changed remarkably. Constant mobility of Lahauli tribes questions the existing facilities & development strategies of government based on tribal development. High volume of migration of Lahaulis has never been the concern of government of Himachal Pradesh and other government & non- government organisations.

The tribes of Himachal Pradesh belong to the famous Indo-Aryan family group. The physical appearances of Lahauli tribes of Himachal Pradesh are almost similar to the Indo-Aryan or Mongoloid. The major tribes of this region include Gaddi tribe, Kinnaura tribe, Lahauli tribe and Gujjar tribe. The Lahaulis reside at the tribal district Lahaul & Spiti of Himachal Pradesh. Lahauli is a generic term that includes many castes like Brahmins, Rajputs, Thakur’s, Bodhs, Sippies, Lohars, etc., those who are living in Lahaul Valley. Geographically, Lahaul & Spiti district is the largest in Himachal Pradesh, accounting for 24.85 per cent of the State’s area. It is inhabited by 31,564 persons, and the density of population is two persons per sq. km compared with 123 persons per sq. km for the state (Census of India, 2011). The Lahaul valley remains cut off from the rest of the world for more than six months in a year due to heavy snowfall. The Lahaulis were accorded the tribal status after independence, considering the tough geo-climatic conditions of the region and their socioeconomic backwardness.

According to census 2011, the scheduled tribes constitute 8.6 per cent of the total population in India. In the last decade, i.e. between 2001 and 2011 census, the decadal growth rate of scheduled tribe population has grown by 23.66 per cent and general population by 17.64 per cent. Some states have experienced negative growth of schedule tribe population (e.g. Nagaland and Andaman & Nicobar Islands). The decadal growth has been highest in Sikkim (85.2 %), Bihar (76.2 %) and Himachal Pradesh (60.3 %). Decadal growth rate among ST’s in Himachal Pradesh was 12.02 per cent between 1991 and 2001 census, which increases to 60.3 per cent between 2001 and 2011 in comparison to decadal growth rate of total population which was 15.54 per cent and 12.94 per cent respectively.

If we look at the decadal growth rate of Lahaul and Spiti District, it is -5.00 per cent between 2001 and 2011 census. This negative growth indicates the migration of Lahaulis to other places. Data shows that decadal growth rate of Lahaul block only is -15.25 per cent and Spiti is 16.65 per cent between 2001 and 2011 census. So this negative population growth is a serious concern.

Due to continuous out-migration from the Lahaul valley, the changing composition of this tribal population would be the serious concern. The decadal growth rate is lowest in Lahaul & Spiti district among all twelve districts of Himachal Pradesh. There is only one district whose decadal growth rate is in negative.

¹ Lugri is a home-made rice/ barley beer prepared in the tribal belt of Lahaul & Spiti.

OBJECTIVES, METHODOLOGY AND DATA BASE

Objectives of the study: The main purpose of this paper was to explore the trend of migration in Lahauli tribes of Himachal Pradesh through the perspective of place of origin. The specific objectives were to know the reasons responsible for migration and to determine impact and consequences of migration on Lahauli tribes of Himachal Pradesh.

Methodology: The present study was done in Lahaul block of Lahaul and Spiti district of the Himachal Pradesh. The paper was based on primary data collected from migrant households (having one or more migrants) at Lahaul (place of origin) valley (or block) of Lahaul & Spiti district of Himachal Pradesh. For the purpose of study, snowball sampling was adopted to select representative sample. A data of 200 samples were collected from all the punchayats of Lahaul valley of Lahaul & Spiti district through a structured interview schedule. The percentage and cross tables were prepared for the analysis.

Distribution of samples: To make the data representative, researcher had covered both the Community Development blocks of Lahaul, i.e. Keylong (Lahaul) and Udaipur of Lahaul & Spiti District of Himachal Pradesh. Data has been collected from 78 villages come under 26 punchayats of Lahaul.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data collected from the place of origin, with respect to the objective of the study, the findings of this study are discussed next:

TRENDS OF MIGRATION

It is very important to know the type of migration to know the trends of migration.

TYPES OF MIGRATION

High rate of Migration in Lahaulis should be a matter of concern and should be discussed in academic as well as community level. It is very important to know the type of migration while keeping track of time and distance. Time and distance, changes the whole scenario of migration.

Table-1

Proportion of migration in relation to time and distance

Sr. no	Migration	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Type of Migration (distance)		
	Inter district	194	97.0
	Inter state	6	3.0
2	Type of Migration (time)		
	Seasonal Migration	21	10.5
	Temporary Migration	22	11.0
	Permanent Migration	157	78.5

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

The table 1 revealed that inter district migration was highest among Lahaulis, which was 97 per cent and interstate migration was very low (i.e. 3 %). The data clearly indicates that Lahaulis sets a short distance in migration, the kind of needs and facilities they want are easily completed in nearby district Kullu. Apart from this, they already have a community in Kullu, where adjustment for migrants becomes easy.

The researcher also tried to find out the migration with respect to time, where data shows that most of the migrations, i. e. 79 per cent were permanent in nature followed by 11 per cent temporary and 10 per cent seasonal migration. The respondents told that before 1950s most of the migrations used to be

seasonal for the purpose of income, which were also mentioned in Harcourt (1871), Diack (1897), Mamgain (1975) and in many other studies.

REASONS RESPONSIBLE FOR MIGRATION

There are many reasons of migration. It may be economic, social, political & environmental. Push and pull factor also plays an important role in migration. Migration is not always the choice of migrants, but sometimes it may be a forceful migration too.

Figure-1
Distribution of responses regarding Reasons of Migration

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

The responses regarding reasons of migration were very diverse. Figure 1 revealed that the reasons like employment (17%), education (12%) and family settlement (9%) dominating the other reasons which were health issues (4%), family conflict (2%), harsh geographical conditions (2%), business purpose(6%) etc. Most of the respondents had given more than one reasons, where for 13 per cent respondents, employment and education (combined) were also one of the reasons. Approximately 15 per cent said employment, education and family settlement as their major reasons of migration. Family settlement may be one of the major reasons of Lahauli Migration, because Lahaulis avoid separation of family. They try to keep their family as joint family. That is why, by mutual understanding, they make property in Kullu to settle at least one brother.

Land distribution is limited in Lahaul because of mountains which cover most of the area of Lahaul and Spiti district. Data shows that 35 per cent of the households claimed that they have land holding of

25-40 bighas² followed by 26 per cent having land holding of 15-25 Bighas followed by 24 per cent having land holding of 5-15 bighas. Only 12 per cent had more than 40 bighas. These land holdings covers both agriculture and non- agriculture land.

If we talk about the occupation of the households, data shows that the main occupations of Lahaulis are Agriculture. Around 92 per cent of the respondents responded, agriculture as their main occupation, perhaps 60 per cent has also subsidiary occupation along with agriculture. 41 per cent said government employment and pension after retirement as subsidiary occupation and 19 per cent said that they have some small business, homestay and hotels etc. These 60 per cent are employee in any Govt. department or having their own business in Lahaul. The population living in Lahaul is either they don't have opportunity to migrate or they have good income from Lahaul. Hard life of winters of Lahaul forces you to think about migration once in life for sure.

During the data collection in the field, researcher found that most of the elderly people of Lahaul believe that most families in Lahaul have less agricultural land, and if it is also distributed in 3-4 brothers, then the land that comes in the part of a brother will not be enough for the family's livelihood. This was the reason that Lahaulis tried to settle one or two of their brothers in Kullu by mutual understanding and contribution. An elderly man from Jahalaman claimed that the Polyandrous was also one of the major reasons of migration in earlier days.

Some people also believed that after the trade was closed with Tibet, they had no income instruments, so Lahaulis started migrating towards Kullu for income. Many people bought land in Kullu by selling horses, because now the income was reduced from the horse. On one hand, the trade with Tibet was stopped due to the war with China, and on the other hand, the road was constructed in Rohtang Pass for lahaul.

The table 2 describes the clear migration trend of Lahauli tribes towards the nearby district Kullu.

Table-2
Migration trend with respect to place of destination & Time

Place of destination	Migration year of family				Total
	1951-1970	1971-1990	1991-2010	After 2011	
Manali-Katrai	15	30	22	0	67(33.5%)
Katrai-Kullu	5	3	15	1	24(12%)
Kullu-Bhuntar	5	25	61	3	94(47%)
Manikaran Belt	0	2	0	0	2(1%)
Banjar-Sainj belt	1	1	0	0	2(1%)
Outside Kullu	1	2	5	3	11(5.5%)
	27(13.5%)	63(31.5%)	103(51.5%)	7(3.5%)	200(100%)

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

The above table 2 depicted the clear picture of trends of migration in Lahauli tribes of Himachal Pradesh. Table shows that during the year 1991-2010, out-migration (51%) was highest in Lahaulis, followed by in the year 1971-1990 (31%). Overall, the Kullu-Bhuntar area was the first choice for the migration (47%), followed by Manali-Katrai area as a second choice (34%).

Data shows that 30 per cent of respondent's families migrated to Kullu-Bhuntar area in 1991-2010, followed by 13 per cent of respondents in 1971-1990. In the year 1971-1990, Manali-Katrai region was dominated as the first choice of destination (15%), followed by Kullu -Bhuntar (12%). The table

² There is no "standard" size of bigha. The size of a *bigha* varies considerably from place to place. The size of Bigha is different in different areas. 1 Bigha in Himachal Pradesh= 0.2 Acre & 5 Bigha = 1 Acre

also pointed out that during the initial phase of migration in 1951-1970, Manali-Katrai region was the first choice of Lahauli migrants as destination.

Respondents also told researcher that Temporary migration was large during 1970s to 1990s, because in this period Lahaulis started coming outside from the valley for education and government employment. After 1990s they started settling in different parts of Kullu district, they form community there. Lahaulis have also started investing money in the education of their children, business, and in the property at Kullu. Later the migration changed from individual migration to family migration, as data shows that 84 per cent of the respondents said that three and more than three members were migrated outside Lahaul.

Respondents told that family size were bigger due to polyandry or joint family system, so most of the male members migrate to kullu and Churah during winters for earning & they used to work in fields as agriculture labour and as construction labour in Kullu and as a wood cutter workers in Churah valley of Chamba district.

During the initial phase, Lahauli migration used to be rural to rural migration, because at that time people of Lahaul migrates to kullu for earnings and the only major option of earning was labour in agriculture and horticulture. Few people who had resources, bought land in Kullu for agriculture and horticulture purpose. After 1990's the migration trend has changed to rural to urban migration. There may be many reasons for this change, high hike in the prices of land in Kullu, better income from agriculture in Lahaul too, most of the Lahauli retirees had pension as social security so they have purchased house for residential purpose only. Their capacity to work in agriculture and horticulture decreased, or they don't want to work as they had enough money to lead a dignified life.

The practice of migration can also be closely associated with boom in apple market in early 1960s and tourism market in 1990s, which also attracted Lahaulis towards Kullu and Manali. One respondent from Phura told that increasing scope of apple orchards in Kullu in late 1950s had attracted lahaulis towards kullu. It is also important to note that transport & communication facilities improved in Lahaul after 1965, when Rohtang pass was opened for vehicles. This may be one of the reasons of increased percentage of out migration of Lahaulis.

HEALTH, EDUCATION AND MIGRATION:

In addition to water, food and income, education and health facilities are important for settling anywhere in today's world. The identity of a decent and developed society is the good education and health system of that society. It is very important to know the value of education for the development of society.

Table-3

Responses regarding Health care facilities

Sr. no	Health care facilities	Yes	No
1	Health Centre in Village	117 (58%)	83 (41.5%)
2	Major surgical facilities	7 (3.5%)	193 (96.5%)
3	Private hospitals/ clinics	2 (1.0%)	198 (99.0%)
4	Emergency ambulance facilities	170 (85.0%)	30 (15.0%)
5	Aware about the healthcare programmes	106 (53.0%)	94 (47.0%)

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

It was observed from the table 3, that 58 per cent respondents had health care facilities in their villages in the form of PHC, CHC, District hospital, Ayurvedic health Centre and Sub- Centre and the remaining 42 per cent of the villages did not have any kind of health care facility.

The data shows the pathetic condition of Health care facilities in Lahaul, around 97 per cent respondents replied that they don't have the major surgical facilities in their village and 99 per cent said that there is no private hospital and clinics in their village. Around 85 per cent accepted that they have accessibility of emergency ambulance facilities, but due to network problems and heavy snowfall during winters this facility has no benefit for them. The data also revealed that 53 per cent respondents were aware of healthcare programmes, but most of them know about Polio programme only, some of them were aware of ICDS programmes. A very few respondent aware about the health card facility for Below Poverty Line (BPL) families, Health reimbursement for government employees, free delivery and medicine for pregnant women in government hospitals.

Figure-2

Availability of Health care facilities at respondent's village

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

Note: PHC- Primary health Centre, CHC- Community health Centre, NA- Not available

The types of health care facilities available in villages have been shown by Figure 2, which indicates that only 4 per cent of respondents had the facility of district hospital, 5 per cent had community health centers and 5 per cent had Ayurvedic centers in their villages. According to the responses, number of sub-centers in Lahaul was 26 per cent, but in only few sub-centers, doctors were posted. Around 18 per cent of respondents had primary health centers in their villages.

Table-4

Responses regarding Education Facilities

Sr. no	Education Facilities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Availability of Schools	188	94.0
2	Type of School		
	Government School only	181	90.5
	Both Govt. and Private School	7	3.5
	No School	12	6.0
3	School in Village up to Class		
	Primary	76	38.0
	Middle	41	20.5
	High	7	3.5

	Sr. Secondary	64	32.0
	No School	12	6.0
4	Respondents want to graduate their children from Government degree college (Kukumseri).		
	Yes	12	6.0
	No	188	94.0
3	Preference for education from Lahaul up-to Class		
	Primary	5	2.5
	Middle	3	1.5
	High	77	38.5
	Secondary	47	23.5
	College	9	4.5
	No study in Lahaul	59	29.5

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

The above table 4 shows the status of education in Lahaul. About 88 per cent of the respondents responded that their village has a school, out of which 38 per cent of the respondents had only primary schools in their village till date. Approximately 32 per cent responded that there is a senior secondary school in their village and 6 per cent said that there is not even a single school in their village. The number of private schools was almost non-existent. There were only one or two private schools in Keylong and Udaipur in the Lahaul Valley.

During the data collection some respondents said that the schools closed due to lack of students in their village, because the Lahaulis preferred to teach their children in Kullu. There were also many senior secondary schools where the number of students was very less. These schools were on the brink of closure. One of the respondents from Udaipur told that if their child has to go out and compete with other children then it is very important to teach them in good English schools.

There is only one Government degree college (Kukumseri College) in Lahaul. And the phenomenal thing is that 94 per cent of respondents did not want to teach their children in that college. They also had strong reasons behind their reaction. There are limited subjects in the college, respondents from the Tod Valley, the Gahar Valley and the Jahalman-Tandi region of the Pattan valley said that they have to spend the same amount in Kukumseri, as they spend in Kullu or Shimla. They said that they have their own house in Kullu, so it would be better for them to teach the children there. Apart from this, children did not get many facilities in Lahaul. Lahaul did not have any engineering and other professional colleges.

When it comes to basic education, many people believe that education up to Class X and Class XII is good in Lahaul. Data reveals that 39 per cent of respondents want their children to study high school in Lahaul and 24 per cent wanted to study senior secondary school in Lahaul. Data also shows that 30 per cent of respondents were also those who did not want to teach their children in Lahaul. They believed that if their children study in Lahaul, they would not be able to compete with others. Respondents said that most teachers, who are outside of Lahaul, leave school after completion of 3 years and then lack of teachers in schools. Now the irony was that teachers from Lahaul also did not like to work in Lahaul.

OTHER FACILITIES AFFECTING MIGRATION

The present era is the era of social media and technology. You can connect with the world by your mobile and laptops, and if you don't have connectivity, it will definitely affect your life.

Table 5 revealed that the other facilities such as newspapers, mobile networks, internet etc. were also not in good condition in Lahaul. Due to the heavy snowfall, these facilities are impossible in winters. You can't get newspaper, internet stops working for months. You cannot fill any kind of competitive exams, you cannot come out of Lahaul to give any kind of exams. This was the reason that most students were preparing for exams by staying out of Lahaul. People migrate to Kullu to avail these facilities and for the better future of their kids.

Apart from this, data also shows that 99 per cent of respondents were not satisfied with health facilities and about 95 per cent of them were also unhappy with education facilities in Valley.

Table-5
Facilities affecting life at Lahaul

Sr. no	Facilities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Availability of Newspaper		
	Yes	3	1.5
	Sometimes	22	11.0
	No	175	87.5
2	Winters affect studies		
	Yes	51	25.5
	Sometimes	121	60.5
	No	28	14.0

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

Due to climatic conditions, people of the valley did not get any benefit from public transport in the winter. Around 96 per cent of the respondents admitted the lack of services as major reason of migration, whereas 91 per cent of the respondents accepted that the better facilities at place of origin can decrease the rate of migration.

EFFECTS OF MIGRATION

Lahauli migrants continue to maintain close relations with their native place. Migration often separates families, some members have to leave their homes and others are left behind in the original place. Migration can have positive as well as negative effects on the life of the migrants as well as on the families left behind.

Table-6
Effect of migration on the life of respondents

Sr. no	Effects of Migration	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Migration affect life at origin		
	Yes	64	32.0
	No	61	30.5
	Little	75	37.5
2	Remittance received from migrants		
	Yes	13	6.5
	Sometimes	47	23.5
	No	140	70.0
3	Help of children in studies		
	Yes	113	56.5
	No	58	29.0
	NA	29	14.5

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

Table 6 revealed that when respondents were asked about the remittance, only 7 per cent responded that they receive remittance from migrants, 23 per cent replied that they got monetary help from migrants in need only and 70 per cent replied that they had enough for their livelihood and not getting anything from migrants. When the respondents were asked that, do the migrants help in the education of your children? Around 57 per cent replied that their children got some kind of financial or residential help from migrant family members, 29 per cent replied that they got no help and 14 replied NA (non-applicable), as they were not applicable for question.

The findings of the study also shows that nearly 95 per cent of the migrants had good relations with the family members who were left behind. 77 per cent said they were benefited from the migration of the family member. Approximately 70 per cent respondents believed that migration affects their lives more or less.

Table-7
Effect of migration at place of origin

Sr. no	Characteristics	Options	
		Yes	No
1	Migrants have good relation with origin family	190 (95.0 %)	10 (5 %)
2	Affect Domestic workload	169 (84.5 %)	31 (15.5%)
3	Benefitted by migration of family member	155 (77.5 %)	45 (22.5 %)
4	Migration affects culture	129 (64.5 %)	71 (35.5 %)

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

Table 7 revealed that 85 per cent respondents reported that migration affects their domestic workload. Respondents said that migration has increased their domestic workload, earlier more people used to do the same work, now less people has to do the same. Farming work has also changed with time. The effects of outer people have always influenced the culture. Same happened in case of migration of Lahaulis also. Data revealed that 65 per cent respondents replied that migration affects their culture. People changed their way of life, many rituals and traditional values are on the verge of death. Many respondents also believed that many Lahaulis have started marriages outside Lahaul, which is why they are moving away from their home and culture.

IMPACT OF MIGRATION ON FAMILY RELATIONS

Migration has social, emotional, and psychological impacts on an individual as well as on community. Family relationships are also not untouched by the impact of migration. Long-term migration strains relationships between spouses, parents and children.

Table-8
Responses regarding Migration and its impacts on family relations

Sr. no	Migration & family relations	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Migrants join family at origin during happy and sad moments		
	Yes	140	70
	No	1	.5
	Sometimes	59	29.5
2	Emotional impact of migration on families left behind		
	Family breakdown	8	4.0
	Fragmentation of social networks	52	26.0
	Psychosocial stress	94	47.0
	Anxiety	38	19.0

	Any other	2	1.0
	No effect	6	3.0
3	Family relation deteriorates due to migration		
	Yes	30	15.0
	No	89	44.5
	Partly	81	40.5
4	Feeling after migration		
	Feeling of rejection	19	9.5
	Loneliness	105	52.5
	Happy	2	1.0
	Bad	71	35.5
	Nothing	3	1.5

Source: Primary data

(n=200)

The present paper indicates that 15 per cent respondents accepted that family relations deteriorate due to migration, 41 per cent respondents were partially agreed with the statement and 44 per cent were not in the favor that migration deteriorates the family relations. The 15 per cent respondents who believe that family relationships are getting worse due to the migration perhaps this could be exactly the opposite of above statement. It may be possible that 15 per cent of migrations were happened due to a bad relationship.

Moving to a new place, a migrant has to face many problems. Not only the migrant, but the families left behind also faces many problems. Emotional Problems are one of them. The paper revealed that almost 95 per cent respondents faced emotional problems when their family members first migrated. Of these, 47 per cent faced psychosocial stress, 26 per cent accepted that fragmentation of social networks was one of the outcomes, 19 per cent faced anxiety and least 4 per cent experienced family breakdown. The paper also shows that 52 per cent respondents felt lonely after migration of family members. Around 36 per cent felt very bad when their family members migrated and 10 per cent felt rejected.

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded from the above analysis of the available data that the trends of migration have changed with time. During the initial phase of Lahauli migration, Manali-Katrai region was the first preference of migrants as destination place. This was because of many reasons, first, Manali is most nearest place to Lahaul and the climate of Manali is almost similar to Lahaul. As Lahaulis were involved in trade with Ladakh & Tibet, Manali used to be the place for traders during winters. From the point of income also, Manali-Katrai region was perfect for orchards. The land was also not much costly before 1970s. After mid 1980s the preference of destination place changed to Kullu-Bhuntar region as Lahaulis started migrating from the valley for education and government employment. Kullu region had a number of private schools and one government degree college too. After early 1990s again the trend of migration changed. Now the permanent migration of lahaulis increased as they started owning residential houses in the pockets of kullu, the migration for study and jobs increased till that time. At that time, Lahaulis were becoming financially strong. There may be many reasons for this change, high hike in the prices of land in Kullu, better income from agriculture in Lahaul too, most of the Lahauli retirees had pension as social security so they have purchased house for residential purpose only. Their capacity to work in agriculture and horticulture decreased, or they don't want to work as they had enough money to lead a dignified life. People of Lahaul also acknowledge that their development has taken place due to migration.

The finding of the study indicates that the reasons like employment, education and family settlement dominating the other reasons which were health issues, family conflict, harsh geographical conditions,

business purpose etc. Most of the respondents had given more than one reasons, employment and education (combined) and employment, education and family settlement were their major reasons of migration. Family settlement may be one of the major reasons of Lahauli Migration, because Lahaulis avoid separation of family. They try to keep their family as joint family. That is why, by mutual understanding, they make property in Kullu to settle at least one brother. Poor health and education facilities forces Lahaulis to migrate outside the valley. Not only the health & education but the poor facilities of internet, non-availability of newspaper were also the reasons of migration. Poor transportation and connectivity during winters also affects life in Lahaul. The heavy snowfall affects every aspects of life as well as the facilities too.

Migration affects the life of migrants in new place as well as the families left behind. Respondents admitted that migration affects their domestic workload, migration affects their culture. People changed their way of life, many rituals and traditional values are on the verge of death. Not only the migrant, but the families left behind also faces many problems. Emotional Problems are one of them. The paper revealed that people at origin faced emotional problems when their family members first migrated. These problems were psychosocial stress, fragmentation of social networks, some of them faced anxiety and few experienced family breakdown also. The paper also showed that families left behind felt lonely, very bad & felt rejected after migration of family members.

Population density is often seen as a cause of migration, but in case of Lahauli migration the case is different, here density is very low and it is decreasing according to census 2011. It helped to reduce poverty in origin and played a great importance in changing lifestyle of locals. On the other hand, we can also say that permanent migration may become hindrance to development of origin place because it transfers resources to place of destination. Migration leads to an acute shortage of labour in place of origin. Shortage of labour in lahaul has encouraged mechanization, most of the agriculture come under power tillers.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The main occupation of the majority of Lahaul's population is farming, but during winters farming is not possible & they don't have any other ways of income. In such a situation, providing employment considering climatic conditions there for 6 months in winter, may prove effective for reduction in migration.
2. There is a need of to improve the state of education and health, and keeping the valley connected with the world for 12 months, which together can play an important role in reducing migration.
3. Migration can also be reduced by promoting the winter games, promoting culture and eco-tourism in Lahaul valley. An initiative is very much needed in this field.
4. There is a need to establish village based small scale industries, which can be proved milestone for the reduction of migration.
5. After the opening of tunnel, people of Lahaul have a lot of expectation from tourism, people believe that reverse migration will be encouraged. So, there is a need to develop proper infrastructure and facilities to facilitate tourists.

REFERENCES

1. Agnew, P. D. (1897). Gazetteer of the Kangra District – Part II to IV- Kullu, Lahul and Spiti. New India: Indus Publishing Company.
2. Bird, K., & Deshingkar, P. (2009). Circular Migration in India- Policy briefing No 4. World Development Report 2009, London: Overseas Development Institute.
3. Dayal, H., & Karan, A. K. (2003). Labour Migration from Jharkhand. New Delhi: Institute for Human Development.

4. Department of Economics and Statistics. (2014). Socio-Economic Indicators of Himachal Pradesh 2014-15. Shimla: Department of Economics and Statistics Himachal Pradesh.
5. Government of India. (2011). Census of India 2011. New Delhi: Ministry of Home Affairs, retrieved from <http://www.census2011.co.in/census/state/himachal+pradesh.html>.
6. Harcourt, A. F. P. (1871). The Himalayan District of Kooloo, Lahoul and Spiti. London: Allan & Co.
7. Hutchison, J., & Vogel, J. (1933). History of the Punjab Hill States. Vol. II.
8. Kumar, A. (2004). Development and Mobility among Lahula Community in Himachal Pradesh. Unpublished PhD thesis, Punjab University Chandigarh.
9. Mangain, M. D. (1975). Himachal Pradesh District Gazetteers Lahul & Spiti. Chandigarh: Greater Punjab Press.
10. Ministry of Tribal Affairs Government of India. (2014). Report of the high level committee on socio-economic, health and educational status of tribal communities of India. Retrieved from <http://www.kractivist.org/wp-contest/uploads/2014/12/trival-committee-report-may-june-2014.pdf>.
11. Mosse, D., Gupta, S., Mehta, M., Shah, V., & Rees, J. (1997). Seasonal Labour Migration in Tribal (Bhil) Western India. Report to DFID India.
12. National Commission for Scheduled Tribes. (2007). A Handbook. Retrieved from <http://www.aicte-india.org/downloads/handbook%20for%20Scheduled%20Tribes.pdf>
13. National Sample Survey Organization, (2007-2008). Employment & Unemployment and Migration Survey: NSS 64th Round. New Delhi: Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India (GOI).
14. Negi, T. S. (1976). Schedule Tribe of Himachal Pradesh. Meerut: Raj Printers.
15. Sahni, R. N. (2006). Lahoul: The Mystery Land of Himalayas. New Delhi: Indus Publishing Company.
16. Thakur, N., Savitri, & Bhalla, T. C. (2004). Characterization of some Traditional fermented foods & beverages of Himachal Pradesh. Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge, 3 (3), 325-335.
17. Verma, V. (2012). Lahaul: A Tribal Habitat in Himachal Pradesh. Delhi: B.R. Publishing Corporation.

WEBSITES

1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bigha>